

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Dioxouranium(VI)

RENU AHUJA and K. DWIVEDI*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

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The presence of mixed-ligand complexes in biological systems and their applications in analytical chemistry have stimulated interest in the study of formation of such species¹. A number of mixed ligand complexes of UO_2^{2+} ion have been studied with aminopolycarboxylic acids, such as ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid with coordination number (CN) = 6, nitrilotriacetic acid with CN = 4 and iminodiacetic acid with CN = 3². Ethyleneglycol-bis-2-aminoethylether tetraacetic acid (EGTA) is an octadentate aminopolycarboxylic acid and forms stable binary complexes with many metal ions at low pH³. However, it has been used in the mixed ligand complexation studies in solution only by a few workers⁴. This prompted us to investigate several mixed-ligand complexing systems using this octadentate ligand. In this paper we report the results obtained for the study of 1 : 1 : 1 UO_2^{VI} -EGTA-aspartic acid/glutamic acid systems.

Results and Discussion

The ratio of moles of alkali required per mole of ligand/metal 'a' was determined from the titration curves and plotted against pH. The titration curves obtained for binary and ternary complexes involving aspartic acid and glutamic acid were found to be identical in nature and thus only the curves obtained with the former ligand are presented (Fig. 1). The equilibria reactions were analysed and the constants were evaluated.

The proton dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the 1 : 1 binary complexes were determined by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁵ as modified by Nayan

and Dey⁶. Evidence for the formation of the mixed-ligand complex in solution was obtained by the comparison of the experimental 1:1:1 mixed-ligand titration curve-6 with the theoretical composite curve T (Fig. 1). It is found that

Fig. 1. UO_2^{VI} -EGTA-aspartic acid system; $\mu = 0.10 M$ (NaNO_3), temp. 25° .

mixed-ligand titration curve is located to the right of the composite curve in the initial pH range. This non-superimposable nature of the experimental curve with that of the theoretical composite curve provides the evidence for the liberation of greater

number of protons in the presence of the two ligands, which can be attributed to the formation of mixed-ligand complex. Further in the pH range where the formation of mixed ligand complex is evidenced, the formation of either of the binary complex is not complete, hence the ternary complex can be formed by the simultaneous coordination of the two ligands to the metal ion⁷. This can be represented by equation (i),

where A = EGTA, B = aspartic acid/glutamic acid and *a* is the moles of alkali per mole of metal ion in the mixed ligand system. Equation (1) shows the liberation of four protons during the formation of ternary complex which should account for the consumption of four equivalents of alkali and hence an inflection at *a* = 4 is expected in the mixed-ligand titration curve. However, the inflection in the ternary titration curve is noted at *a* = 2 which suggests that the ternary species so formed is diprotonated which can be represented as

This diprotonated species is found not to remain stable for a wide pH range as evidenced by the fact that the inflection observed at *a* = 2 does not continue long. At pH above 5.2, the value of *a* increases continuously indicating the additional release of protons which can be attributed to the deprotonation of the above formed diprotonated ternary species. This can be represented by the following equilibria :

Considering the diprotonated mixed-ligand complex in equilibrium as a single predominant species,

its deprotonation constants are calculated by the reported method⁶. Formation constants of the mixed-ligand complexes are calculated by the method described below. The equilibrium reaction for the formation of diprotonated 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex formation is given by

(charges being omitted for simplicity)

$$K_{\text{MH}_2\text{AB}} = \frac{[\text{MH}_2\text{AB}]}{[\text{M}][\text{HA}][\text{HB}]} \quad (2)$$

If *C_M*, *C_A* and *C_B* are the total concentrations of metal ion, ligands H₂A and H₂B respectively then

$$C_M = [\text{M}] + [\text{MH}_2\text{AB}] \quad (3)$$

$$C_A = [\text{H}_2\text{A}] + [\text{HA}] + [\text{MH}_2\text{AB}] \quad (4)$$

$$C_B = [\text{H}_2\text{B}] + [\text{HB}] + [\text{MH}_2\text{AB}] \quad (5)$$

The concentrations of other possible species like hydroxo and polymeric are negligible at lower pH range where equilibrium studies are made and hence have not been considered. Charges have also been omitted for the sake of clarity.

On adding equations (4) and (5),

$$C_A + C_B =$$

$$[\text{H}_2\text{A}] + [\text{HA}] + [\text{H}_2\text{B}] + [\text{HB}] + 2[\text{MH}_2\text{AB}] \quad (6)$$

Since *C_M* = *C_A* = *C_B*, replacing *C_A* and *C_B* by *C_M* and rearranging equation (6),

$$[\text{MH}_2\text{AB}] = C_M - 1/2([\text{HA}]x + [\text{HB}]y) \quad (7)$$

and

$$[\text{M}] = 1/2([\text{HA}]x + [\text{HB}]y) \quad (8)$$

where, *x* = ([H]/*K_A^H* + 1), *y* = ([H]/*K_B^H* + 1)

During the simultaneous chelation of both the ligands to the metal ion, the total hydrogen ion liberated are supposed to be neutralised simultaneously by the titrant base solution. If *a* is

NOTE

the moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand H_2A or H_2B , it will be shared simultaneously by H_2A and H_2B owing to their respective equal contributions to the hydrogen ion concentration. Therefore, other pertinent equations maintaining the material balance are

$$1/2 (aC_A + [H] - [OH]) = [HA] + [MH_2AB] \quad (9)$$

$$1/2 (aC_B + [H] - [OH]) = [HB] + [MH_2AB] \quad (10)$$

Solving for [HA] and [HB],

$$[HA] = \frac{C_A - 1/2(aC_A + [H] - [OH])}{[H] / K_{1A}^H} \quad (11)$$

and

$$[HB] = \frac{C_B - 1/2(aC_B + [H] - [OH])}{[H] / K_{1B}^H} \quad (12)$$

Now substituting the values of $[MH_2AB]$, $[M]$, $[HA]$ and $[HB]$ from equations (7), (8), (11) and (12) respectively, in equation (2),

TABLE I—VARIOUS EQUILIBRIA AND THEIR CORRESPONDING EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANT

Temp. = 25°, $\mu = 1.10 M$ (NaNO₃)

Equilibrium	log equilibrium constant
$H_2EGTA^{-2} \rightleftharpoons HEGTA^{-3} + H^+ \quad (K_1^H)$	-8.87
$HEGTA^{-3} \rightleftharpoons EGTA^{-4} + H^+ \quad (K_2^H)$	-10.47
$H_2Asp \rightleftharpoons HAsp^- + H^+ \quad (K_1^H)$	-4.38
$HAsp \rightleftharpoons Asp^{-2} + H^+ \quad (K_2^H)$	-9.79
$H_2Glu \rightleftharpoons HGlu^- + H^+ \quad (K_1^H)$	-4.59
$HGlu^- \rightleftharpoons Glu^{-2} + H^+ \quad (K_2^H)$	-9.54
$UO_2^{2+} + EGTA^{-4} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2EGTA^{-2}) \quad (K_{ML})$	13.44
$UO_2^{2+} + Asp^{-2} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2Asp)^0 \quad (K_{ML}')$	9.11
$UO_2^{2+} + Glu^{-2} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2Glu)^0 \quad (K_{ML}')$	8.53
$UO_2^{2+} + HEGTA^{-3} + HAsp^{-1} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2H_2EGTA.Asp)^{2-} \quad (K_{MLL}')$	8.30
$UO_2^{2+} + HEGTA^{-3} + HGlu^{-1} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2H_2EGTA.Glu)^{2-} \quad (K_{MLL}')$	7.95
$(UO_2H_2EGTA.Asp)^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2H_2EGTA.Glu)^{2-} \quad (K_{MLL}')$	7.95
$(UO_2H_2EGTA.Asp)^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2HEGTA.Asp)^{-3} + H^+ \quad (K_{1MLL}^H)$	-5.94
$(UO_2HEGTA.Asp)^{-3} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2.EGTA.Asp)^{-4} + H^+ \quad (K_{2MLL}^H)$	-8.64
$(UO_2H_2EGTA.Glu)^{2-} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2.HEGTA.Glu)^{3-} + H^+ \quad (K_{1MLL}^H)$	-5.99
$(UO_2HEGTA.Glu)^{3-} \rightleftharpoons (UO_2.EGTA.Glu)^{-4} + H^+ \quad (K_{2MLL}^H)$	-8.72
$UO_2HEGTA^- + UO_2HAsp^+ \rightleftharpoons (UO_2H_2EGTA.Asp)^{2-} + UO_2^{2+} \quad (K_D)$	-2.95
$UO_2HEGTA^- + UO_2HGlu^+ \rightleftharpoons (UO_2.H_2EGTA.Glu) + UO_2^{2+} \quad (K_D)$	-2.96

$$K_{\text{MH}_2\text{AB}} = \frac{C_M - \frac{1}{2}([\text{HA}]x + [\text{HB}]y)}{\frac{1}{2}([\text{HA}]x + [\text{HB}]y) [\text{HA}][\text{HB}]} \quad (13)$$

The values of equilibrium constant corresponding to various equilibria reactions are calculated and are presented in Table 1.

Experimental

Standard solutions of CO₂-free sodium hydroxide (0.10 M), nitric acid (0.01 M), uranyl nitrate (0.01 M) and sodium nitrate (1.0 M) were prepared. Solutions of 0.01 M each of aspartic acid, glutamic acid and disodium salt of EGTA were prepared by direct weighing. All the chemicals used were of reagent grade and the solutions were prepared in CO₂-free doubly distilled water.

An Elico LI-120 pH meter (accuracy \pm 0.01 pH unit) with a glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. It was calibrated before and after each titration with buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 9.20 at 25°.

The following mixtures were prepared and titrated against 0.10 M sodium hydroxide solution under nitrogen atmosphere : (1) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M), (2) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + EGTA (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M), (3) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + EGTA (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + UO₂^{VI} (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M), (4) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + amino acid (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M), (5) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + amino acid (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + UO₂^{VI} (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M) and (6) HNO₃ (2.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + EGTA (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + amino acid (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M) + UO₂^{VI} (1.0 \times 10⁻³ M). Experiments were carried out keeping the initial volume of each mixture

as 50 ml and an ionic strength of 0.1M (NaNO₃) at 25 \pm 0.2°. In Fig. 1, the curve numbers represent the plot of pH vs *a* corresponding to titration mixtures 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 while T represents the theoretical composite curve.

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